

UPBRINGING OF PERFECT HUMAN IN THE WORKS OF A.NAVOI

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An outstanding Uzbek poet Alisher Navoi demonstrated both theoretically and practically the richness of the Uzbek language that it possesses strength and the ability to express different views. His raised the Uzbek language to an unprecedented level by skillfully expressing its deep meaning in colourful artistic images of the Uzbek language, showed that it possesses vast spaces of splendor, power, attractiveness and intelligence.

Introduction. Alisher Navoi (is his pen-name, but his original name was Nizomiddin Mir Alisher, who was on the 9th February, 1441 in Herat, and passed away on 3rd January, 1501) was an outstanding Uzbek poet, thinker and states person. Alisher Navoi's grandfather from his father's side, was a foster-brother of Umar Sheikh, i.e. a son of Amir Temur, who then served Umar Sheikh and Shahruh. His father, Giyasiddine Bahodir, was a close man to Aulkasim Babur's family, who took part in the administration of the government. His mother, whose name is unknown, was a daughter of Sheikh Abusaid Chang, who was one of the famous individuals of government of Kabul. Alisher Navoi's childhood coincided with the last years of Shahrukh's reign. He was brought up with the Temerids, in particular, with future King Hussein Baykaro. The portrait of A.Navoi with King H.Baykaro by T.Jaloliddinov At the age of four he went to school, could retell poetry by heart in Turkish and Persian languages. The genius and intelligence of Navoi in the World of Poetry is growing. His every poem, every gazelle, every line awakens a sincere feeling in all hearts. This is a great genius, the idea of five great and priceless sculptures.

Love, loyalty, true justice, Stick to the faces of friendship forever. Alisher was distinguished by his reading and manners. Navoi was known to people as a talented poet at the age of fifteen years old. All his poems in Uzbek were included in four-volume collection "Hazazin ul-Maoni," "Miracles of Childhood," "The Rarity of Youth," "Middle Beauty," "Old Age Benefits," but his Persian poems were included in the Devony Foniy collection. Although he was not a school teacher or teacher, but he did a great job in teaching. Navoi, was a sponsor of education, has always paid close attention to school and educational activities. The establishment of schools and madrassas to educate and teach working children was one of the main tasks facing the state, and it was in love with scientists and teachers. Alisher Navoi wished the young generation to acquire knowledge and good human qualities. In his poem "Mahbub ul-Kulub" the poetic profession of the teacher, emphasizing that he owes his teacher, in any case, even if he was the king. If someone taught you a letter, you can't pay a hundred treasures for it. In many of his works Navoi put forward the idea of bringing up children. Ul-Abror, Farhad and Shirin, Leyli and Mejnun, who entered Hamsa, were raised by children. Among them is the philosophy of "Hayrat ul-abror" which covers social, political and ethical issues. The poet encourages children to be educated, respectful, honest, pure, generous, respect their parents and adults, to grow up honest and fair people. In the sixth chapter of the poem "Hayratul-abror" poet gives valuable feedback about education. The tenth chapter of the poem puts forward the idea of truthfulness

and accuracy. The poet's eleventh story is also remarkable, it tells about science and people's knowledge. He encourages people to acquire knowledge and respect scientists. Education is one of the key factors in human education.

Main part. Navoi's exceptional talent was demonstrated at the age of three or four. It was then that he first learnt by heart poetry, and he read poetry in a circle of respected people and was impressed. It was a gazelle of the famous poet in his childhood Alisher Herat, Amir Kasim Anwar. According to the literary scholar Izat Sultan, the memory of one and a half years of Alisher gazelles says that there is another tradition that goes beyond a child's capabilities: not only poetry in medieval Asia and the East and even large books had to be memorized by the child, and one of the most important tasks of pedagogy was to educate the child's ability to remember. Alisher once told by heart this poem to his mentor Mevlano Lutfiy: If the sun shades the face, my eyes always rolls tear. There will appear stars in the sky when there is no sun. After reading the gazelle, Lutfiy said: "If I could, I would exchange all my poems for this hemistich, i.e. incomplete song". This praise was a great reward for the twenty-year-old poet. Navoi respected the community, protected the interests of all honest people and promoted good ethics. In his work he paid special attention to ethical issues. According to the poet, good manners are one of the noble qualities of the human being. Good manners are good-natured, attentive and kind. A respectful person will always are respected and honoured. Polite words are the best virtue for everyone. Everyone has a duty to honor and respect parents, brothers, sisters, friends. Navoiy encourages parents to bring up their children with such qualities, who should have the best human qualities: If you have good manners, Then try to teach people a lesson. Try to teach every value, Obeying the decency, do your best and give a lesson. Especially in the poem "Farkhod and Shirin" high human qualities and properties of mankind deeply influence on the spirituality of young readers and help them be worthy people and homeland.

Conclusion. Alisher Navoiy was not only a poet, but also a great scientist and thinker of his time. It is difficult to imagine the development of science and culture of that period without Navoi. The article contains heartfelt words that our great poet was an ordinary and kind man in life. We know that the Hazrat Navoiy, i.e. noble man, was not married, and of course he had no children. But he loved children and lived a passionate life. Enthusiasm and passion were so great that others adopted their children and showed them their father's love. There were many such children in the great poet. Alisher Navoiy fought for the benefit of the people throughout his life. He was a good example to everyone. He did a great job of organizing the work, financially and morally encouraging them, building hospitals and hospitals. He took part in the excavation of small channels and canals, in the construction of roads and caravan sheds, road safety, education, youth education, building dormitories for them, recruitment of teachers and etc. He led noble deeds remembering the spirit of the dead. He also took care of improving cemeteries and suburbs. He sang man, but called only to do good things and to be always in good ehavior to everybody. He encouraged people always to be patient, to be quite humble, generous and more generous. We can see such manners from his following poem:

What is given by Lord, take it without resistance,
And be patient, whatever your destiny is

Don't listen to all the nonsense,
Refrain from all sorts of gossip and talk

Here is one more example from his creative work: My Dark Eyed One... Come my dark eyed one come and show your kindness, Weave a nest for yourself, in the depth of my pupils. Turn the garden of my heart into a flowerbed, for the blossom that is your face, And the rest your slender form so like the sapling in the garden that is my heart. Splash the hooves your brave steed in me heart's blood. And weave a leash for your dog from the tendons of my sad soul. O Heaven, if at the foot of the mountain of separation my dust is discovered, Knead it into the dough and sculpt from it a powerful stone mason. If you wish to encapture hearts in love by a meeting with you, Curl your long hair into ringlets. There is little the gardener can do to stop the advance of the fall, Should he even spike the roof of his garden with pine needles. O my friend, should I suddenly die at the sight of perspiration on your face, Bathe me in rose water and lay me to rest in a shroud made of rose petals. Navoiy, if you can put your heart all into a bouquet of joy, Pick a sheaf of wheat and touching a flame to it let this candle be the revelation of the nosegay.

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